

An Innovative Methodology for Revealing Home Appliances' Consumption Patterns to Transform Energy Management and Maintenance Strategies

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Abstract. Developing efficient techniques for energy optimization and conservation requires a thorough understanding of the patterns of energy usage among different home appliances. This study looks into the energy usage patterns of several household appliances and assesses how well machine learning methods classify these patterns. Appliances are categorized into three groups: constantly on devices, program-based on-demand devices, and non-program-based on-demand devices. Key statistical features such as periodograms, mean, and standard deviation are extracted for machine learning classification, employing DenseNet 1D, XGBoost, LightGBM, SVM, KNN, and Random Forest. The findings show DenseNet and LightGBM performing exceptionally well, with nearly 98% accuracy in classifying constantly-on and program-based devices, indicating their potential in optimizing energy usage.

Keywords: Non-intrusive load monitoring · Energy consumption patterns · Household appliances · Energy management strategies.

1 Introduction

Energy management assumes a central role in the rapidly evolving technological landscape, where the demand for power continues to escalate. Using and optimizing energy resources has become an imperative task, not only for economic reasons but also for addressing environmental concerns. The growing need for sustainable energy practices has led to the field of energy management, which

focuses on efficient utilization, conservation, and monitoring of energy resources [1]. Navigating the complexities of modern energy challenges underscores the increasing realization that a targeted approach is essential for achieving optimal outcomes. This is particularly evident in the domain of home appliances, where energy consumption patterns offer valuable insights into usage behavior. Understanding these patterns can transform energy management strategies, providing opportunities for improved efficiency and reduced environmental impact.

Efficient energy management strategies can also extend the lifespan of devices, contributing to long-term sustainability and reducing the overall environmental footprint. By implementing maintenance strategies tailored to the specific energy consumption patterns of appliances, it is possible to optimize their performance and prolong their operational life [2]. This holistic approach along with anomaly detection methodologies not only improves energy efficiency but also promotes sustainable practices, aligning with the broader goals of environmental conservation and resource management [3].

Researchers have employed various methodologies for appliance classification, addressing challenges in energy usage optimization. In [4], a decision tree algorithm applied to smart meters' power consumption data achieved a 74% classification rate. Another study in [5] developed a smart home appliance classification system using LSTM deep learning, achieving competitive performance and enabling real-time classification through a Raspberry Pi and a mobile application. [6] presents a system using plug-based sensors and machine learning for household appliance identification, demonstrating an 85% correct identification rate, aiming for energy and cost savings.

While significant progress has been made in appliance classification and power consumption anomaly detection, there's a noticeable gap in the integration of supervised and unsupervised learning methodologies. Most studies focus on one approach, utilizing either supervised techniques like decision tree algorithms or unsupervised methods for anomaly detection. The potential for a more comprehensive solution lies in the unexplored integration of both. A unified framework that combines the strengths of both paradigms is missing, highlighting a crucial gap in current research. Addressing this could greatly improve the accuracy, adaptability, and real-time performance of energy management systems, pushing the field towards more effective strategies.

The remainder of the paper is set up as follows: Section 2 describes the different power consumption patterns of home appliances. Section 3 analyzes the methodology followed in the current study, highlighting the statistical features extracted. Section 4 discusses the results during an experimental phase while the conclusions are summarized in the last Section 5.

2 Home appliances pattern categories

Home appliances can be categorized into distinct groups based on their operational characteristics and usage patterns. This categorization facilitates a better understanding of energy consumption behaviors and aids in the development of

targeted energy management strategies. In this paper the home appliances are categorized into 3 classes: constantly on devices and on-demand devices (with program-based and non-program-based subcategories) based on work [7].

Constantly on devices are appliances that remain operational continuously, typically to maintain specific conditions or functionalities within the household. These appliances often include refrigerators, freezers, or others with less power consumption such as WiFi routers and security cameras. Some features of constantly on devices are that they run autonomously and exhibit a recurring consumption pattern. Especially for the refrigerator, it continuously cycles on and off to regulate internal temperatures, resulting in a recurring consumption pattern. Additionally, constantly on devices consume a significant amount of energy as a result of their continuous operation, making them major contributors to the overall consumption of energy in the home. Figure 1 illustrates the pattern of recurring power consumption of a refrigerator.

Fig. 1. Power consumption pattern of a refrigerator

On-demand devices are appliances that are activated only when needed, based on user input or specific triggers. These devices can be further classified into two main categories: program-based and non-program-based.

Program-based on-demand devices are appliances that require user to select specific program for their operation. These devices follow predefined programs or settings to perform specific tasks. Common examples of program-based on-demand devices include washing machines, dishwashers, and ovens. Some features of these devices include variable power consumption, which depends on the selected program and load. Moreover, program-based devices exhibit distinct power consumption patterns characterized by recognizable phases corresponding to different stages of operation. For example, a washing machine typically undergoes phases such as heating, washing, and spinning during its operation cycle. Each phase has distinct power requirements, contributing to the overall power consumption pattern of the device. Figure 2, first graph presents the power consumption pattern of a washing machine. As can be observed, the three different

phases are distinct: heating from 17:20 to 17:55, washing from 17:55 to 18:20, and spinning from 18:20 to 18:30.

Non-program-based on-demand devices are appliances that operate based on simple user input, typically involving only on/off functionality. Common examples of non-program-based on-demand devices include kettles, toasters, and hair dryers. This type of devices exhibit a simple power consumption pattern characterized by an initial peak followed by a gradual reduction in power consumption as they reach their operating state. Figure 2, second graph illustrates the power consumption pattern of a steam iron.

Fig. 2. Power consumption pattern of a steam iron

The above categorization of home appliances into 3 groups based on their operational characteristics and usage patterns is essential for gaining insights into energy consumption behaviours and for developing targeted energy management strategies. The degradation of home appliances and their energy efficiency is directly influenced by their category. Constantly-on devices degrade over time due to continuous operation, impacting their energy efficiency, while the energy efficiency of on-demand devices is related to the frequency of their usage. Understanding these degradation patterns is essential for implementing effective maintenance and energy conservation strategies. Moreover, the categorization of appliances also plays a significant role in assessing the potential energy impact of malfunctions as presented in 1 [8].

3 Methodology

The methodology of the proposed system is presented in Figure 3. The procedure starts with the preprocessing phase. Then, the preprocessed data are used as input in the statistical feature extraction. In this phase, statistical features important for the classification process are extracted. Subsequently, the PCA method is applied to reduce the total number of features, and finally, multi-class classification methods are applied to categorize the input data into one of the

Table 1. Increase in energy consumption per category

Categories	Home appliances	% of consumption increase	
		Specific Faults	Minor malfunctions Major malfunctions
Constantly On	Refrigerator/ Freezer	Compressor +50	5-10% 15-70%
Program Based	Washing machine	Heating phase +76	
	Dishwasher	Heating phase +33.60	5-15% 20-35%
	Dryer	1st Heating phase +36.97	
Non Program Based	Oven	Faulty Thermostat +10	
		Slight overheating +50	5-7% 10-20%
	Water Heater	Faulty Thermostat +10	
		Slight overheating +50	
AC/HVAC	Blocked filter +50		

three classes: 0 for constantly-on devices, 1 for program-based devices, and 2 for non-program-based devices.

Fig. 3.

3.1 Data Preprocessing

Preprocessing is a really crucial phase of the method aimed at cleaning and preparing the raw data for further analysis [9]. This process ensures the reliability and accuracy of subsequent analyses. Missing values are filled, as well as outliers and duplicate instances are removed. Z-score analysis and box plots were used to detect outliers, followed by appropriate methods to remove them. Mean imputation was used to fill missing values with the mean of the respective features. Finally, duplicate instances were detected and removed in order to ensure the integrity of the dataset.

3.2 Extract Statistical Features

Table 2 illustrates the extracted statistical features of the proposed system. These features are crucial for the examination of the input data since they offer insightful information that the subsequent classification technique requires. The periodogram was used to detect the periodic instances within the dataset, while the mean and standard deviation (std.) was used to estimate the variability of the data. Additionally, the rolling mean and std. compute the moving average and std. over a specified window size, offering information on the trend and variability of the data over time. Finally, the proportion of data which are above a predefined threshold describes the duration during which the device remains enabled. An extensively analysis of the presented statistical features is presented in the following subsections.

Table 2. Extracted Statistical Features

Statistical Features	Parameters
Periodogram	5 frequencies with highest PSD
Mean, Std.	-
Rolling Mean and Std.	30, 60, 90, 120 min.
Proportion Above a Set Threshold	ranges from (1-10 W)
Matrix Profile	10, 15, 20, 25, 30 min.

Periodogram The periodogram is a well-known method used in signal processing and spectral analysis to calculate the power spectral density (PSD) of a signal. It provides information about the frequency components of the time series data and is computed using the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) of the signal [10]. Mathematically it can be described as follow:

Let $x[n]$ be a discrete-time signal of length N , where $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N - 1$. The Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) $X[k]$ of the signal $x[n]$ is calculated as [11]:

$$X[k] = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x[n]e^{-j2\pi nk/N}, \quad (1)$$

where $X[k]$ is the k -th frequency component in the frequency domain, $x[n]$ represents the signal in the time domain, j denotes the imaginary unit, which is the square root of -1 , k is the frequency index in the frequency domain and it ranges from 0 to $N - 1$ and N the total number of samples in the signal $x[n]$.

The PSD of the signal, denoted as $P(\omega)$, represents the distribution of power across different frequencies. It is calculated using the squared magnitude of the

DFT $X[k]$, normalized by the signal length N [12]. Mathematically it can be described as follows:

$$P(\omega) = \frac{1}{N}|X[k]|^2, \quad (2)$$

where $\omega = 2\pi f$ is the frequency in radians per sample, and f is the frequency in Hertz. The frequency f can take values from 0 to $\frac{f_s}{2}$, where f_s is the sampling frequency.

The periodogram $P(\omega)$ provides a spectrum of the signal $x[n]$, indicating the distribution of power across different frequencies. Peaks in the periodogram correspond to dominant frequency components present in the signal. In this paper 5 frequencies with the highest PSD were selected as features.

Mean, Standard Deviation, Rolling Mean and Standard Deviation Statistical measures such as the mean and standard deviation provide essential information into the central tendency and variability of a dataset. Rolling statistics, such as rolling mean and rolling standard deviation, provide a dynamic perspective by calculating these metrics over sliding windows of data. The rolling mean and standard deviation mathematical equations are described as follows.

The rolling mean over a window of size w at time t is defined as the average of the last w observations:

$$\text{Rolling Mean}_t^w = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{i=t-w+1}^t x_i \quad (3)$$

In a similar manner, the rolling standard deviation at time t over a window of size w is calculated as:

$$\text{Rolling Standard Deviation}_t^w = \sqrt{\frac{1}{w} \sum_{i=t-w+1}^t (x_i - \text{Rolling Mean}_t^w)^2} \quad (4)$$

Rolling mean and rolling standard deviation provide information into the local behavior of the dataset, allowing for the detection of short-term trends and fluctuations. In this paper, four different ranges for the rolling statistics were used 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes, aiming to capture any temporal patterns or trends within the dataset at varying levels of granularity. These time periods were selected to provide a thorough examination. These time periods were selected to provide a thorough examination of the behavior of the data across various time scales, enabling the detection of cyclic patterns, short and long-term trends, and spikes.

Proportion above a set Threshold A statistical feature representing the proportion above a threshold is used to indicate the amount of power usage exceeds above a predefined threshold. This measure is really important in detecting whether a device is constantly-on, as it reveals the amount of time the device

runs above the predefined threshold. The threshold is typically defined based on the lowest power consumption of the device and is not set to zero to account for potential power consumption during idle situations.

The proportion above a predetermined threshold P_{above} can be calculated as follows:

$$P_{\text{above}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N I(P_i > \text{threshold})}{N}, \quad (5)$$

where P_{above} is the proportion of minutes where power consumption is above the set threshold, N is the total number of minutes in the observation period, P_i is the power consumption in the i th minute and $I(P_i > \text{threshold})$ is the indicator function that returns 1 if the power consumption in the i th minute is above the set threshold, and 0 otherwise.

Matrix Profile The matrix profile provides information on the similarity between subsequences within a time series dataset [13]. Euclidean distance metric is used to calculate the matrix profile of each time series data [13]. The procedure for calculating the matrix profile with different window sizes is described by the following algorithm:

1. For each window size m :
 - Initialize an array MP_m of length $N - m + 1$.
 - Using the Euclidean distance, iterate through the time series data X and calculate the minimal distance for each subsequence of length m .
 - Assign to $MP_m[i]$ the minimum distance found.

For each window size m , the matrix profile MP_m is calculated as follows:

$$MP_m[i] = \min_{1 \leq j \leq N-m+1} \sqrt{\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} (X[i+k] - X[j+k])^2}, \quad (6)$$

where $MP_m[i]$ represents the nearest neighbor distance (minimum distance) of $X[i]$ to any subsequence of length m in X , i ranges from 1 to $N - m + 1$, ensuring that the sliding window fits entirely within the time series dataset X and j represents the starting index of the subsequence in X .

3.3 Classification methods

DenseNet 1D DenseNet (Dense Convolutional Network), is a deep learning architecture known for its dense connectivity pattern, where each layer is connected to every other layer in a feed-forward way. This dense connectivity addressing challenges associated with gradient vanishing and feature reusability, leading to improved parameter efficiency and better gradient propagation. DenseNet architectures typically consist of dense blocks, where convolutional layers are densely connected, and transition layers, which downsample feature maps to control the

model's growth [14]. This architecture has been widely used in various computer vision tasks, including image classification, object detection, and segmentation.

In this paper, a variation of DenseNet called DenseNet 1D designed for one-dimensional (1D) data, such as time series or sequential data, was used. DenseNet architectures are suited for image data with spatial dimensions, while DenseNet 1D is designed to handle sequential data with time dependencies. In DenseNet 1D, the 2D convolutional layers of the original architecture are replaced by 1D convolutional layers, and both the filter/kernel size and the pooling layers are adjusted accordingly from 2D to 1D. Due to its ability to capture temporal patterns and dependencies present in sequential data, DenseNet 1D is well-suited for a variety of applications in signal processing, sequential data categorization, and time series analysis.

Fig. 4. Architecture of the DenseNet-1D

Extreme Gradient Boosting Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) is an ensemble learning algorithm that enhances the scalability and performance of conventional gradient boost techniques using gradient boost methods. To iteratively reduce a given loss function, XGBoost builds an ensemble of weak learners, usually decision trees, in a sequential manner [15]. By combining the predictions from each individual tree in the ensemble, the final forecast is produced. XGBoost can effectively to handle sparse data making it an appropriate solution for high-dimensional datasets. Mathematically, the prediction \hat{y}_i for a given data point x_i can be represented as [15]:

$$\hat{y}_i = \phi(x_i) + \sum_{k=1}^K f_k(x_i), \quad (7)$$

where $\phi(x_i)$ represents the initial prediction, typically the mean of the target variable, and $f_k(x_i)$ denotes the prediction of the k -th tree in the ensemble.

XGBoost employs a gradient-based optimization algorithm to iteratively refine the predictions of each tree. At each iteration, the algorithm seeks to minimize a loss function $L(y_i, \hat{y}_i)$, which measures the discrepancy between the true target y_i and the predicted value \hat{y}_i . The objective function to be minimized can be formulated as [15]:

$$\text{Obj}^{(t)} = \sum_{i=1}^n L(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{(t-1)} + f_t(x_i)) + \Omega(f_t), \quad (8)$$

where $\hat{y}_i^{(t-1)}$ represents the predicted value at iteration $t - 1$, $f_t(x_i)$ is the prediction of the t -th tree, and $\Omega(f_t)$ is a regularization term that penalizes the complexity of the tree to prevent overfitting.

LightGBM LightGBM is a gradient boosting framework which employs a tree-based learning algorithm that builds an ensemble of decision trees in a sequential manner. However, unlike traditional gradient boosting methods, LightGBM utilizes a novel technique called Gradient-based One-Side Sampling (GOSS) and Exclusive Feature Bundling (EFB) to improve training speed and reduce memory usage [16].

Mathematically, LightGBM minimizes the following objective function [16]:

$$\text{Obj} = \sum_{i=1}^n L(y_i, \hat{y}_i) + \Omega(\Theta), \quad (9)$$

where $L(y_i, \hat{y}_i)$ is the loss function measuring the discrepancy between the true target y_i and the predicted value \hat{y}_i , and $\Omega(\Theta)$ is a regularization term on the model parameters Θ . The algorithm iteratively updates the model parameters by minimizing this objective function, leading to the construction of an ensemble of decision trees that collectively minimize the overall loss.

4 Experimental-Set up and Results

In this section, a detailed overview of the experimental setup is presented, including the equipment used for data collection and the size of the data. Additionally, a thorough evaluation of the classification methods presented is conducted, along with a comparison with state-of-the-art methods.

4.1 Experimental Set-up

In order to gather data from common household appliances that fall into the three different classes constantly-on devices, program-based devices, and non-program-based appliances, smart plugs were exploited in the experiment setting. Z-Wave smart plugs (i.e., FIBARO Wall Plug (FGWPF-102 ZW5)) renowned for their easy installation were selected as all one needs to do is plug it into a power outlet. Televisions (TVs), refrigerators, freezers, dishwashers, washing machines, steam irons, and dryers, that fall into a particular group within the classifications above are among the home appliances that were being monitored. These appliances were selected because they are common in ordinary homes and show different energy use patterns. Table 3 presents the overview of the experiment setup. As the dataset was unbalanced SMOTE techniques were applied [17].

Table 3. Experiment Overview

Home Appliance	Granularity	Instances	Mean of Monitor
Fridge	1 min	65 days * 1440 min.	Smart Plug
Freezer	1 min	29 days * 1440 min.	Smart Plug
Dishwasher	1 min	47 days * 1440 min.	Smart Plug
Washing Machine	1 min	71 days * 1440 min.	Smart Plug
Steam Iron	1 min	65 days * 1440 min.	Smart Plug
Dryer	1 min	41 days * 1440 min.	Smart Plug
TV	1 min	46 days * 1440 min.	Smart Plug

4.2 Results

The results illustrated in Table 4 present an overview of the performance of different machine learning techniques that use the extracted statistical features. LightGBM consistently demonstrates high accuracy under different conditions, achieving an overall accuracy of 0.984 and maintaining robustness in the evaluations of the three classes with an accuracy greater than 0.97 in all cases. Similar results were observed using DenseNet, with an overall accuracy close to 0.98 and accuracy on each class above 0.97. Additionally, DenseNet showcases strong recall rates, highlighting its reliability in correctly identifying positive instances, with recall scores exceeding 0.97 for all classes. Finally, while XGBoost and SVM offer moderate performance across metrics, KNN and Random Forest exhibit relatively lower accuracy and precision, indicating areas for potential improvement.

Table 4. Experimental results of the classification methods

Techniques	DenseNet	XGBoost	LightGBM	SVM	KNN	Random Forest
Accuracy	0.979	0.941	0.984	0.974	0.952	0.945
Accuracy (Constantly-on)	0.988	0.9765	0.988	0.984	0.957	0.972
Accuracy (Program-based)	0.976	0.958	0.984	0.958	0.947	0.954
Accuracy (non-Program-based)	0.969	0.887	0.970	0.958	0.953	0.899
Precision (Constantly-on)	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.996	0.996	0.998
Precision (Program-based)	0.972	0.912	0.972	0.975	0.972	0.902
Precision (non-Program-based)	0.974	0.934	0.986	0.942	0.902	0.935
Recall (Constantly-on)	0.999	0.981	0.999	0.983	0.963	0.975
Recall (Program-based)	0.972	0.961	0.982	0.964	0.953	0.952
Recall (non-Program-based)	0.974	0.896	0.971	0.965	0.954	0.902
F1 score (Constantly-on)	0.999	0.981	0.996	0.996	0.972	0.996
F1 score (Program-based)	0.971	0.932	0.982	0.976	0.961	0.934
F1 score (non-Program-based)	0.972	0.915	0.974	0.954	0.929	0.921

The confusion matrix for each evaluated machine learning technique is depicted in Figure 5. Regarding DenseNet, it is evident that for the first class (constantly-on), only 3 instances out of 256 were misclassified. However, for the second class (Program-based) and the third class (non-Program-based), the number of misclassified instances was higher, with 9 misclassifications in the second class and 12 in the third class. Nonetheless, the distinction between constantly on and on-demand devices remains clear, with only 3 instances misclassified. Similar results were observed using the LightGDB and SVM method.

On the other hand, the results of XGBoost, KNN, and Random Forest were worse compared to the other three methods. Specifically, in XGBoost, there were 6 misclassified instances in the first class, and 11 and 27 in the other two classes, respectively. Similar results were observed with the other two algorithms, with 11 and 7 misclassified instances in the first class, and 25 and 36 in the other two classes, respectively. These findings highlight the comparatively poorer performance of these models in accurately classifying instances across different classes.

An extensive evaluation was conducted using three home appliances refrigerator, washing machine and steam iron to further evaluate the performance of the three best machine learning models DenseNet, LightGBM and SVM. The evaluated devices were not included in the training phase of the models, making this evaluation particularly significant for assessing the generalization capability of the models. Table 5 presents the results of the evaluation method. In the case of the refrigerator, both DenseNet and LightGBM achieved lower accuracy compared to SVM, indicating the effectiveness of SVM in correctly classifying instances from these devices despite not being trained on them. While DenseNet and LightGBM exhibited competitive performance, particularly on the Washing Machine and Steam Iron datasets, SVM consistently outperformed them, suggesting its effectiveness in accurately classifying behavior on new and unseen devices. However, all methods were able to detect the power consumption pattern with an accuracy consistently above 0.90.

Table 5. Results of the DenseNet, LightGBM and SVM on test set

Device	Methods	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
Refrigerator	DenseNet	0.810	0.999	0.799	0.897
	LightGBM	0.824	0.999	0.824	0.903
	SVM	0.963	0.999	0.963	0.981
Washing Machine	DenseNet	0.990	0.989	0.986	0.987
	LightGBM	0.982	0.988	0.990	0.989
	SVM	0.985	0.987	0.983	0.986
Steam Iron	DenseNet	0.985	0.987	0.983	0.986
	LightGBM	0.983	0.989	0.986	0.989
	SVM	0.987	0.986	0.989	0.988

Fig. 5. Confusion matrix of the classification methods

5 Conclusions

In this study, energy consumption patterns of home appliances were investigated, and the performance of machine learning techniques in classifying these patterns was assessed. Distinct categories of home appliances based on operational characteristics and usage patterns were identified, including constantly-on devices, program-based devices, and non-program-based devices. Machine learning algorithms, including DenseNet, LightGBM, and SVM, demonstrated high accuracy and robustness in classifying appliance categories using statistical features extracted from energy consumption data. These models show promise for real-world applications such as smart home energy management systems, enabling the identification of energy-consuming appliances and optimization of energy consumption. Regarding future work, developing a system capable of identifying each individual home appliance rather than categorizing them into predefined classes will be a challenging task.

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